

**Design and Simulation of Novel Demand
Response Management Systems under
Enhanced TSO-DSO Interaction**

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SUMMARY

Electric power systems are facing major challenges as fossil fuel generation is replaced with renewable generation, which is often characterised by variable behaviour. This increases the need for resources to be used to guarantee voltage and frequency stability and to ensure power quality. At the same time, an increasing number of flexible demand and storage systems is located at distribution level. These resources could potentially be available to provide network services if they are aggregated effectively. To achieve this, however, the roles of the diverse network stakeholders – transmission systems operators (TSOs), distribution systems operators (DSOs) and aggregators – should be reshaped. In tandem with this, the way real-time electricity markets are organised must also be adapted to reflect the new operating environment.

The SmartNet project (<http://smartnet-project.eu/>) compares five different TSO-DSO interaction schemes and different real-time market architectures with the aim of finding out which one could deliver the best compromise between costs and benefits for the system in the pan-European context. An ad-hoc-developed platform is used to carry out simulations on three benchmark countries – Italy, Denmark and Spain – whose results are used to perform a cost-benefit analysis. This analysis compares the benefits drawn by the system with the costs of ICT needed to implement each coordination scheme. In parallel, three demonstration projects (pilots) are deployed to test specific technological solutions to enable monitoring, control and participation in ancillary services provision of flexible entities located in distribution networks.

This paper looks at the national cases of Spain and Denmark during the first two years of the SmartNet project whereby the project explores the role of aggregator to study in depth the participation in ancillary services of flexibility from DSO-connected batteries in radio-based stations in the city of Barcelona (Spain) and thermal inertia from swimming pools in summer houses in Jutland and Esbjerg (Denmark). The role of aggregator in both the simulations and the physical pilots is analysed to test novel management systems and communication schemes with Distributed Energy Resources (DER) by means of direct and indirect controls. On the one hand, direct control uses traditional bidirectional communication to harness flexibility while presenting several issues in providing scalability. On the other hand, indirect control broadcasts unidirectional signal that is interpreted by the flexible assets, simplifying the communication when millions of DERs are considered at the expense of reducing control or response certainty.

1 INTRODUCTION

The contribution of intermittent renewable energy sources (RES) to the European electricity supply is steadily increasing in the last years [1]. On the one hand, the variability resulting from this new paradigm requires a growing reserve to be used for providing ancillary services (ASs) –in particular, system balancing, congestion management and voltage control– so as to maintain system stability. On the other hand, RES plants are replacing big power plants based on coal and gas technologies, which were the traditional providers of such reserve. Therefore, the management of ancillary services markets by the national Transmission System Operator (TSO) is becoming increasingly complex.

In addition to RES generation, Distributed Energy Sources (DER) –distributed generation and flexible loads, very often connected to distribution grids– are also becoming important actors in the electricity sector. Hence, an important question to be answered is whether DER might replace large generation sets in the provision of ancillary services to the system through an increasing level of cooperation between TSOs and the different Distribution System Operators (DSOs).

The Clean Energy Package proposal issued by the European Commission in November 2016 assigns a role to DSOs for local congestion management but not for balancing, whose management would remain in the hands of the TSOs [2]. It can be questioned whether maintaining a rigid decoupling between balancing and congestion management potentially risks leading to inefficient system operation. The European research project SmartNet (<http://smartnet-project.eu>) aims at investigating how the TSO-DSO interaction for the acquisition of ancillary services (AS) from DER connected to distribution networks can be optimised, by defining and comparing five potential coordination schemes [3], [4].

One of the countries where the SmartNet project is focusing is Spain. Balancing and associated ASs become increasingly complex and costly activities in the Iberian market because the share of highly-variable production from RES in the Spanish generation mix is relatively large. In the presence of such RES technologies in the market, the need for reserves to balance supply and demand increases. In addition, the increasing number of DER and consumers may lead to grid congestion issues. However, demand-side management programmes have only been implemented at transmission level and applied to large industrial loads in Spain, such as in the

so called “interruptibility service”. By assuming proper regulatory, economic and technology schemes, it is envisioned that demand-side management will be applied at distribution level as well, following the trend in several European countries.

Meanwhile, in Denmark, another country where the SmartNet project is implementing a pilot, more than 40% of the power load is covered by wind power on average and it will increase in the future [5]. The limited predictability of this fluctuating wind resource more often leads to imbalances. These imbalances in Denmark are, to a large extent, handled by the large thermal loads, inertia of the district heating systems, and balancing with neighboring countries. Most district heating systems have the possibility of using either boilers, heat pumps or gas engines. These production units are scattered geographically and, if activated upon a market price signal, offer a sound platform to deal with grid stability concerns. Hence, the SmartNet pilots represent a step ahead towards better management of future Spanish and Danish scenarios and eventually future pan-European context with contribution of demand-side flexibility at distribution system level.

2 DESCRIPTION OF FUNCTIONALITIES

In order to assess the potential participation of DER connected at distribution level in the provision of ASs, two pilot projects are being implemented.

2.1 The Spanish Pilot

The pilot aims at implementing balancing services and congestion management for distribution networks through **direct bi-directional signals** coming from an aggregator [6]. This is pushed further downstream to the activation of back-up batteries to reduce the consumption in selected grid regions of, in this case, the city of Barcelona. The pilot involves six primary substations and 20 radio base stations, which are equipped with back-up batteries, and, thus, can be disconnected from the grid when required.

The DSO takes a new role, called Local Market Operator (LMO), to fulfil its balancing responsibilities by acquiring the flexibility of local DER. Based on the grid status, the DSO calculates the flexibility requirements and organises a local market, where different aggregators

offer their flexibility. Once the market is cleared, aggregators perform direct control over the DERs they manage —base stations in this pilot— and check their real-time consumption, since DER's real-time performance will be used by the DSO to settle imbalances and to pay for the services after flexibility activation. The DERs participating in the pilot have relatively fast response times so that their ramp-up events are not significant related to the total activation period. In this design, the activation period is 5 minutes, thus consecutive markets are also organized every 5 minutes. Accordingly, 1-minute maximum response time has been set so that aggregators and their associated DERs reach the final value within that time.

Figure 1. General scheme of the Spanish pilot

As described in Figure 1, the DSO and the LMO in the pilot is Endesa Distribución, the aggregator is ONE and the DERs are radio base stations owned by Vodafone, which is also the provider of the connectivity service —on-site kits and the platform for the aggregator to monitor and control remotely the DER flexibility. In order to represent the effect that competition will have in the acceptance of bids by the aggregator of base stations, the bids that other aggregators can present will be simulated and included in the local market clearing process.

2.2 The Danish Pilot

The main purpose of the pilot is to implement and evaluate the activation of flexibility – in this case, electric heated swimming pools in summer houses - to provide system balancing and grid congestion services at the DSO level using **unidirectional signals** coming from an aggregator. Summer houses have a relatively large and flexible consumption, i.e. the electrical load used to heat pool water can easily be shifted in time due to the thermal inertia from stored water. This makes them particularly well-suited to the provision of ancillary services. The pilot involves 30 summer houses at two geographical areas in Denmark.

The DSO shares common responsibility with the TSO to stabilize the grid. Here, the DSO takes a new role called Local Market Operator (LMO) in a common TSO-DSO market where DERs and traditional assets can bid their flexibility. Based on the grid status, the DSO calculates the response requirements and organises a local market, where different aggregators offer their flexibility. Once the market is cleared, a commercial aggregator broadcasts a signal which is taken by a technical aggregator to deal with the particular complexity of the control systems of these particular DERs.

Figure 2. General scheme of the Danish pilot

As described in Figure 2, the DSO and the LMO in the pilot is Syd Energi, the aggregator is ONE and the DERs are electric heated swimming pools located in summer houses in the northern coast of Denmark.

The main novelty of the Danish pilot is the use of indirect unidirectional control techniques, which are much more scalable. As there is no bilateral “transaction” or communication from the aggregator to DERs, it is far more secure from an information technology perspective. In addition, it is more economical to deploy and offer DERs an indirect yet true participation in the market without using complex DER surveillance systems while DERs keep the final decision to be activated or not.

3 ROLE OF AGGREGATOR

The pilots involve three main participants: the DSO, the aggregator and the DER owner. This section focuses on the role of aggregator in the Spanish and Danish pilots.

3.1 The Spanish pilot

The aggregator must define the bidding strategy and perform the management and activation of the flexibility available in the batteries of a portfolio of radio base-stations. In order to fulfil these duties, the aggregator needs to communicate with DERs through Vodafone’s Energy Data Management (EDM) systems to acquire real-time status and to manage activations. For the communications and processes in the Spanish pilot, a centralised middleware model has been selected, so that there is a sole interface towards outside counterparties. These communications and processes are depicted in Figure 2 and described below:

- a. Aggregation algorithms are based on work from previous phases of the SmartNet project, which yield a foundation for the optimisation of storage units when bidding into SmartNet-alike markets.
- b. There is a constant 1-minute frequency update on the charge and voltage status from the batteries located at radio base-stations, allowing the aggregator to determine its availability for activation.

- c. Based on b) and batteries' constraints, there exists opportunities to bid for up and/or down regulation. This is put into the context of wholesale market prices and their market price signal to derive a bidding strategy, i.e. decide whether to use the limited flexibility now or wait.
- d. When the bidding strategy is set, a formal set of bids are sent to the market platform aggregated by DSO's load-area and enough lead-time to satisfy the bidding gate closure.
- e. Once market is cleared a message is received from the market platform with the clearing price as well as, in case of bid acceptance, the activated volume per load-area.
- f. The aggregator then performs the disaggregation of the accepted bid, i.e. assigns individual activations to each DER to obtain the successful aggregated behaviour. In this case, the aggregator uses direct control of the batteries, which makes the disaggregation process rather trivial since every bid in process d) represents a cluster of individual activations.
- g. Based on the disaggregation process of the successful bids, an activation message is sent to the relevant DERs via Vodafone's EDM.
- h. Thanks to the real-time asset status update described in b), the aggregator has a good observability on the assets and can, thus, verify the activation schedule of each of them or react otherwise.

Figure 2. Process Flow of the Spanish pilot from Aggregator's point of view

3.2 The Danish pilot

The aggregator has indirect control over DERs through a unidirectional signal. As introduced in Section 2, this technique is an important technological advancement incorporated into the Danish pilot. For this control, two different mechanisms have been discussed in the SmartNet project, namely '*priced-based*' and '*scalar-based*'.

3.2.1 Price-based control

In price-based control, the signal sent over represents the price for the consumed energy of each DER for a given time-period. This mechanism allows for the DERs to perform economic optimization and leaves to the DERs the ultimate decision to '*respond*'. A high price signal incentivizes the DERs to consume less, whereas a low-price signal invites them to increase consumption. In this case, the aggregator estimates the overall price-response reaction from DERs on a series of dummy price signals and, based on the inference, submits bids to the market platform. In case of activation, the aggregator broadcasts the price signal that leads to the successful bid.

Due to DERs' price elasticity and the heterogeneous, stochastic nature of DERs' responses, the aggregator faces the challenge of characterizing and describing the relationship between the control signals and the resulting electricity load with enough level of detail to minimize the risk premiums to be added in his bidding strategy so that he can remain competitive.

According to the analysis of the project, while price-based control has numerous advantages, its mechanism presents a challenge with regards to invoking upregulation response (i.e. decreasing consumption). In addition, allowing DERs to make the final decision on their reaction while the aggregator faces the market and sets the DERs energy price at its sole discretion could create an agency issue.

3.2.2 Scalar-based control

To avoid the upward regulation and potential agency issues posed by the price-based control, an alternative scalar-based control is introduced. This mechanism controls DERs through a broadcasted '*scalar*' signal, a number that serves as '*code*' between the aggregator and DERs.

The signal can be unambiguously interpreted by DERs in a pre-established manner. This technique simplifies the process by giving the aggregator a ‘direct’ control over the DER response.

Figure 4. Process Flows of the Danish pilot from Aggregator’s point of view

4 MAIN CHALLENGES IN SETTING UP THE DEMONSTRATION PROJECTS

The pilots initiated their execution phases in early 2018. Before and during the experimentations, there are several challenges on the aggregator side.

4.1 Availability of the DERs

One of the major challenges is limited physical access to and limited use of the DERs, for example, during special events in Barcelona (e.g. Christmas, Mobile World Congress, etc.) in the Spanish pilot and during vacation periods at the summer houses in the Danish pilot.

4.2 Mathematical representation of DERs flexibility

Due to the complex processes behind the DERs flexibility, the aggregator must develop a decent representation of such flexibility in order to perform the bidding strategy that is cost-efficient with the lowest risks possible.

4.3 Complexity in estimating reaction of DERs

Generally, the indirect control methods do not provide simple solutions when DERs lose connection with the aggregator and stop receiving the broadcasted signals.

4.4 Communication set-up

Establishing the communication link between the aggregator and the DERs in both the direct and indirect controls becomes a challenge when thinking on how to implement it in a scalable manner. In the pilots, it is too manual and too much exception-based, hence not scalable. This is the main topic to be observed when evaluating real dissemination potential of these techniques.

5 CONCLUSIONS

Although the Spanish pilot and the Danish pilot have just started their operations and most of the conclusions will be obtained at the end of the experimentation period, there are some very useful experiences in the demonstration projects.

From the aggregator's point of view, the pilots are very useful to test the flexibility that batteries and electric heated swimming pools can provide in real-life operations using the IoT and

indirect control respectively. As a result, the aggregator can redefine the mathematical models of the batteries and the swimming pools, and improve the forecasting of the need for grid services. The operations also enhance the understanding of the patterns of electric flow congestion in urban and suburban areas, thereby allowing the aggregator to refine and optimise his bidding strategies. At the same time, through the pilots, the project has a better understanding of the extended role of aggregator in a business model of aggregating DERs as well as significant associated volume risks (response volume).

Another lesson learned from the pilots is that DERs are highly sensitive to the price of imbalances, since these assets are not as controllable as utility-scale batteries or spinning reserves (turbines). As for the DER owners, the real-life experience of using batteries and heated swimming pools for providing flexibility results in two main benefits. Firstly, the DERs, with a single investment –battery cost and swimming pool cost– can provide not only their primary functions but also incomes from provision of grid-support services. Secondly, the DER owners can perform a strategic re-thinking when acquiring the flexible assets, for example the optimal battery size and technology that best fit the new requirements in terms of number of charge-discharge cycles and/or lifetime.

Additionally, the knowledge and first-hand experience obtained through direct participation in the project like SmartNet is of great value for the development of demand response activities for the industrial partners in the project. Taking into account that Vodafone has more than 100 000 base stations in Europe, representing an equivalent load of around 400 MW –about 200 MW of which corresponds to the flexible part in this pilot, i.e. to load that could be supplied through electric storage systems, the success of the pilot and the possibilities to scale it up can be a very important step towards the flexibilization of demand to facilitate the integration of RES in power systems.

Overall, the experiences from the SmartNet project's simulations and pilots will provide valuable information for research on demand response management systems and their commercial application at the pan-European level in the future.

6 BIBLIOGRAPHY

- [1] Eurostat. “Share of electricity from renewable sources in gross electricity consumption, 2004-2015”. Available on-line at: http://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/statistics-explained/index.php/File:Share_of_electricity_from_renewable_sources_in_gross_electricity_consumption,2004-2015_%25_T2_New.png (last accessed: 22 January 2018).
- [2] European Commission. “Proposal for a DIRECTIVE OF THE EUROPEAN PARLIAMENT AND OF THE COUNCIL on common rules for the internal market in electricity”. COM(2016) 864 final. Brussels, 30 November 2016.
- [3] G. Migliavacca, M. Rossi, H. Gerard, M. Dzamarija, S. Horsmanheimo, C. Madina, I. Kockar, G. Leclerq, M. Marroquin, H. Svendsen, “TSO-DSO coordination and market architectures for an integrated ancillary services acquisition: the view of the SmartNet project”. CIGRE Session 2018 Paper C5.306
- [4] G. Guida G. Bruno, L. Ortolano, G. Migliavacca, D. Moneta, C. Arrigoni, F. Zanellini, G. Della Croce, M. Baldini, A. Bridi “Smart TSO-DSO interaction schemes and ICT solutions for the integration of ancillary services from distributed generation”. CIGRE Session 2018 Paper C5.307
- [5] Energinet. “New record-breaking year for Danish wind power.” Available on-line at: <https://web.archive.org/web/20160125083857/http://energinet.dk/EN/EI/Nyheder/Sider/Dansk-vindstroem-slaar-igen-rekord-42-procent.aspx> (last accessed: 4 April 2018)
- [6] C. Madina, M. Pardo, J. Jimeno, J. Merino, J. Caus, M. Marroquin, E. Estrade “Exploiting flexibility of radio base stations in local DSO markets for congestion management with shared balancing responsibility between TSO and DSO”. CIGRE Session 2018 Paper C5.109